

LMS (LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM) LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM FEATURES

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INTRODUCTION

Raising the morale of young people and discovering highly qualified specialists among them is at the center of the strong social policy conducted for the youth, for the future and benefit of the youth in our republic.

In the world experience, one of the important goals of higher education is the professional development of students, the formation of their cognitive skills and the practical application of the acquired knowledge, skills, skills and competencies to life. Decree No. PF-5953 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 2, 2020 "Starting from the 2020/2021 academic year, introduce the procedure for gradually transferring the educational process to the credit-module system in the republic's higher education institutions " is said. In this system of students independent to work separated hours share increased _

That's it basically higher education in institutions education system quality increase in order to traditional teaching tools with one in line modern information and communication technologies Create and apply need will be This issue solution to do for to teach intended software tools , including electron educational and methodological complexes work exit need will be Usually computer constant technical tool as place holds _ Thus the student from computer _ placed issue appropriate and fast point in reaching information from technologies appropriate use the basics absorbs .

LMS (LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM) LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM FEATURES

LMS (Learning Management System) or Education management system , education process manage , organize monitoring , and _ _ to learners information present reach for used software tool and from systems is one LMS features the following to be can _ **Online Lessons and Topics:** Program learners for online lessons download and manage opportunity present to reach **Videos and Articles:** Learners for education materials storage and to them access

opportunity present reach (video, article , electronic textbooks). **Tasks and Tests:** To students tasks perform tests _ transfer , and the results manage opportunity present to reach **Interactive Programs and Tasks:** Students interesting and interactive in methods education to get road to put for interactive programs and tasks . **Monitoring and Evaluation:** Readers activity monitoring _ and evaluation opportunity present to reach **Electronic services:** electronic appeals and another opportunities through learners with communication and interactivity . **Statistics and Analytics:** Readers statistics , records , works , and the results evaluation for in the system monitoring activities _ and analytical information present students , teachers , and another education in the field specialists between cooperation and communication opportunities present to achieve **Information Security:** Private data and events safety provide for necessary safety methods . **Platform About Service:** Platform features change the system update , and data base manage opportunity present reach .LMS systems student and teachers for education process perfect to manage help will give and online of education a lot side that he is healed provides . To learn increase , data exchange more facilitate , and of education prospects for good organize to reach in providing helper will be **Main Features:** Learners and Teachers For Application Interface: Platform learners and teachers for easy to use adapts and to users amenities creates _ **Online Lessons and Video Tutorials:** Teachers to the students online lessons and video tutorials present enough . **Tasks and Tests:** Teachers to the students tasks is giving tests spend and the results manage . **Electronic Textbooks and Materials:** Electronic textbooks , pdf files , articles and another education materials storage and to them access opportunity _ **Interactive Programs and Games:** Students motivation to do for interactive programs , games and another students with cooperation opportunity _ **Monitoring and Evaluation:** Teachers students evaluates and their they monitor their activities . **Electronic Communication and Collaboration:** Teachers students with online communication they do and in cooperation they work **Information Security:** Information safety provide , private information protection they do **Statistics and Analytics:** Readers and teachers of activity statistics information they show and analysis to do opportunity _ **Somehow section:** For example , forums , chats , electronic mail , communication pages such as instruction to departments have will be of LMS

Systems Passable Information: Schools and higher study Countries: LMS systems students Change is good education organize reach and assessment increase for schools and higher study countries by wide is being used .

Enterprise and Entrepreneurship: Enterprise and entrepreneurship in the field employees to education pulling given LMS systems in enterprises too learning process organize to monitor _ and in assessment is being used .

Study Centers: Education centers and education courses are also LMS systems through education organize reach and students evaluation for is using

Corporate Education: Corporate organizations LMS systems employees learning , new knowledge get , and activities in assessment they use

Universities and Education Institutions: Universities and education in institutions teachers , students and experienced specialists study process manage for From **LMS systems is using** Learning Management System systems education innovative and efficient in doing important important have being a student and teachers for of education organize to be done and monitoring _ facilitates. Learning Management System (LMS) systems , education in the field news and organizations for efficient and innovative solutions offer is enough

The following addition data LMS systems about : 1. Daily Monitoring and Assessment: LMS systems teachers and students activities watching go , control to do and evaluation opportunity present is enough This is education process efficient manage and each one of the student development control to do help will give .

2. Learning Analytics and Data: LMS systems learners and teachers activities about analytical information present is enough These are data , organizations for education process analysis in doing and new methods in development help give they get **3. Online Portfolio and Personal Leadership:** Students LMS systems for online portfolios and personal leadership to increase help will give . This is the students own development study , personal goals to put and mastered education directions in creating help will give .

4. Mobile Platforms for Adapted to :

Mobile platforms for adapted (mobile-friendly) Learning Management System (LMS) systems , students and teachers for mobile devices (smartphones and through tablets). to education to achieve facilitate for created _ These systems , to users education materials , tasks , lessons and another system functions online way reach enable will give . Many LMS systems mobile to use through applications (apps) . possibility will give . That's it, readers and teachers for to education to achieve makes it easier and everyone in the place from education to use possibility will give . **5. To goals suitable respectively education:** LMS

systems organizations for special education directions to compose possibility will give . To the goals suitable respectively education modules Create and them manage for amenities present is enough **6. Integration** : LMS systems many another systems and services with integration will be done . These are organizations for education system their own another integration into programs do , information exchange and education optimization enable will give . **7. Manual and Indicators:** LMS systems students for manuals , electronic books , video tutorials and indicators present in reaching help will give . This is the students themselves to learn makes it easier . **8. Education Process Management:** LMS systems management functions through to teachers education modules create , tests compilation , results evaluation and in monitoring help will give . **9. Global Cooperation and Communication:** LMS systems students , teachers and organizations global cooperation between and communication opportunities in creating help will give . Forums , communication panels and interactive tools through education more accelerates.LMS systems education in the field innovative solutions offer is enough and to organizations education process efficient management , students to learn facilitate and education systems in development help will give

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